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(Prof. D. Teresa Judice Gamito)

On Mesolithic/Megalithic transition in Cantabria: the archæological evidence for changes in land use and social complexity¹.

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Summary:

Recent work on coastal mesolithic sites in the North of Spain is providing increased evidence of the stability of those populations, living on a year-round basis of exploitation of seasonal complementary resources, with a heavy component of shellfish collecting and fishing. The first occurrence of pottery in these contexts of shell-middens can be dated around 5.500 bp. The earliest postpalæolithic documented use of inland areas -specially in middle and high altitudes- seems to be attested by the presence of 'megalithic' graves. This paper deals with the implications of these different kinds of archæological record for trying to elaborate a regional model of the changes in economic and social structures.

Mesolithic coastal groups in Eastern Cantabrian Spain: recent views.

After seventy five years of research on Mesolithic sites in Cantabrian Spain, our knowledge of human communities in the area shows a pattern of strictly coastal distribution, with many few exceptions. Even in the case of bias due to different site types (i.e. caves or rockshelters *versus* supposed open air settlements), the actual evidence is clearly pointing to population concentration on littoral zones, as opposed to the Late Palæolithic (including Azilian) use of the main river valleys. The functional hypothesis of the contemporaneity of the Azilian and the Asturian as different depositional *facies* of the same groups, expressed especially by Straus in the last years, must be rejected even on the basis of C-14 dates. Last analyses of faunal remains and isotopic composition of shells from recently excavated Asturian shell-midden sites, as Mazaculos Cave, show a pattern of year-round use of the site, with most of shellfish collecting concentrated in late autumn and winter, and the hunting mainly centered in spring and summer. These two activities must have been complemented with forest resources and, significantly, sea fishing.

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A similar system can be identified in other areas along the Cantabrian coast. In the recently excavated site of El Perro rockshelter, a late Magdalenian layer underlies a true Azilian shell-midden deposit, in turn covered by a thick post-azilian mass of shells. The industry, as in the case of the Azilian/Asturian transition, changes acutely from a typical assemblage of Late Upper Palaeolithic tradition, dominated by circular endscrapers and backed bladelets and points, to a very poor representation reduced to some crudely modified or unretouched flakes. The bone industry, that includes typical perforated antler harpoons and points in the Azilian level, disappears almost completely. Finally, mammal remains are reduced to a very minimum if compared with the -maybe overrepresented- volume of shells in post-azilian deposit.

The change from marine molluscs adapted to a rocky intertidal environment in the Azilian, to mussels and oysters in post-azilian *concheros*, even including species adapted to sandy zones (as in the shell-midden at Santimamiñe Cave in the Basque Country) seems to reflect the impact on sea-level rising in the area, and the parallel changes in coastline morphology.

All this evidence points to the presence of groups of hunter-gatherers, exploiting a wide range of resources in restricted coastal areas, but of very high productive potential, as estuaries and marshes. The first occurrence of pottery in these contexts still lacks of sure absolute dates, but can be estimated around 5.500 bp, from the evidence of the French Basque Country site of Mouligna and some dates in Eastern Asturias. Preliminary analysis of the material from the first ceramic level at Mazaculos Cave seems to show no clear rupture with that Mesolithic pattern.

From this date, maybe in coincidence with the first pottery in coastal shell-middens, it seems that the initial occupation of inland zones began. The models proposing demographic pressure as the main factor for this expansion are far from being demonstrated for this concrete area. Instead, the end of the long stability in the use of highly productive coastal environment claims for a more detailed and critical explanatory framework.

Megalithic research in Cantabria

Megalithic occupation is a very recent research topic in Cantabria, where we have a long tradition of affirmations about the lack of true megalithic material, supposing that the impoverished mesolithic-type group reached even the boundaries of the Bronze Age, in absence of true Neolithic developments.

In Eastern Cantabria, a recent survey enables us for tracing a distribution map of sites indicating the use of middle and high mountain areas (in terms of local topography). The wide visibility of most of site groups has been intended as related to a territorial marking system.

The known archaeological evidence in these ones is actually limited to different types of megalithic structures. The megaliths can appear clustered in *neopoli*, in cases delimited by menhirs (as Anguía, Lodos, Hayas-Alto Guriezo, El Hitón-Sejos and others), sometimes located in mountain passes (Sejos, Pico Jano) or dispersed along ridges and divides (Iiso Grande-El Henal), and in level sections of slopes (Los Cuetos, Sopeña, Pedrehitas). With the exception of the group around San Vicente de la Barquera (Piedrahita-La Raiz) in Cantabria, and the extense clusters in the Sierras Planas of Eastern Asturias, located at low altitude coastal ridges, the megaliths are located in middle and high mountain environments, ranging to more than 1.500 m. in Picos de Europa.

Most of the monuments studied to present day show stone structures, including small rectangular chambers of "cistoid" type and stone *tumuli* for the older stages. It is not a characteristic specific for megalithic monuments in Cantabria: the same type of structures are known in Basque Country (*dolmens* of Galupa and El Fuerte) and Asturias (El Llagüezu, Collá Cimera) for ancient moments in mountain areas. In some cases, as documented at La Raiz III site in San Vicente, we find opportunistic structures, using even natural accidents as elements for the building of the monument. Opposite, we are actually a complete lack of evidence for complex architectures, as passage graves and others elaborated constructions.

The grave goods recovered from megaliths in recent excavations, limited to microliths (trapeces), some flint blades and crude polished axes, with only some minimal sherds of pottery (Peña Oviedo, La Raiz), point to a greater antiquity for inland assemblages, the coastal group of San Vicente maybe being the late one, as suggested by the presence of foliated, flat-retouched points. But, in any case, the perduration of human occupation of mountain areas in

connection with lowland coastal groups until Early Bronze Age is clearly attested by a group of relevant symbolic representations ("idols"), that show the continuity of use, or reoccupation of ancient megalithic areas. This is the case of Peña Tú, in the Sierra Plana de Ydiago, the *cromlech* at Collado de Sejos, or the recently discovered "idol of Peña Sagra", an evident example of the presence of a complex symbolic motif from the coast to the high mountain, superimposed on "sacred" spaces in use for more than one millenium.

Preliminary directions for research

The absence of megalithic structures in alluvial plains and valleys can be due to differential preservation of the archaeological record in areas suffering greater pressure of ploughing and other agricultural practices in historical times. These zones are the most suitable for agriculture, but the almost complete lack of information in that sense (no sickle elements or blades wearing traces of use) avoids us to propose a generalization of cereal growing during Neolithic.

In the first stages, the beginning of productive economy seems to rest mainly on shepherding of caprines and ovines, thus requiring the introduction of new exploitative technologies that include domestic animals, but also the partial clearing of inland forested areas. The distribution of sites seems to reflect a land use by "segmentary societies", with relatively small groups. The lack of evidence about habitation sites and the dispersion of megalithic tombs in the landscape, sometimes along several kilometers of mountain ridges, claims for quite mobile pastoralist groups in wide territories. Climatic conditions in mountain areas, and the presence of an intrincated hilly topography with steep slopes are factors against the extensive spread of agriculture, even to present day.

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